

NSF's NOIRLab Postdoctoral Research Fellowship

In 2023, NSF's NOIRLab established the three-year NOIRLab Postdoctoral Research Fellowship, an opportunity for outstanding postdoctoral scholars to carry out independent research broadly related to the mission of NOIRLab. The fellowship is also intended to help develop the next generation of science and technology innovators and leaders in ground-based OIR astronomy.

The Fellow will spend most of their time on an independent research program of their choosing. They will also have the opportunity to work with NOIRLab staff on activities related to the development and deployment of optical and/or infrared capabilities, techniques, data sets, and analysis

tools, in order to, for example, advance their research program and interests. During the first two years of the fellowship, the Fellows will dedicate up to approximately 25% of their effort to a coherent plan of activities that promote diversity and equity in science.

The individuals chosen to be the inaugural NOIRLab Postdoctoral Fellows are Arvind F. Gupta (based in Tucson) and Anniek Gloudemans (based at Gemini North in Hilo).

Arvind completed his PhD in Astronomy & Astrophysics at the Pennsylvania State University. His dissertation explored the design of exoplanet surveys with extreme

precision radial velocity spectrographs, with a particular focus on the detection of Earth-like planets. At NOIRLab, he will continue to [work on radial velocity exoplanet surveys](#) as well as on studies of the formation of hot and warm Jupiters.

Anniek obtained her PhD at Leiden Observatory in the Netherlands, where she worked on observing radio-loud quasars into the cosmic dawn using multi-wavelength data. During her fellowship, she will continue building samples of these rare sources and studying their extraordinary properties. Her goal is to start new outreach initiatives for the local community and set up a mentoring program within NOIRLab.